

Local Government in Austria

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Financial Arrangements

3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Austria: An Introduction

Robert Blöschl and Dalilah Pichler, *KDZ Centre for Public Administration Research Austria*

General Structure and Budgeting

In Austria there are three tiers of administration: the federal level (ministries etc), the *Länder* level and the local level (municipalities, cities). There are nine *Länder* including Vienna and around 2,100 municipalities. All municipalities manage their own budget independently and can own assets of all kind and operate economic enterprises.

Regarding the municipal financial management, municipalities must prepare an annual budget at the end of the year, which shows in detail which revenues and expenditures are expected for the next year. The local council has to approve the annual budget. In any case, the provision of basic services has to be guaranteed and there are strict regulations on how and for which projects the municipality can take on debts.

Revenues

In Austria there are four main sources of municipal revenue:

- shared tax transfers (around 40 per cent of total operational income);
- local and municipal taxes (around 20 per cent of total operational income);
- fees for municipal services incl. utilities and other educational and social services (around 20 per cent of total operational income);
- current transfers (around 10 per cent of total operational income);
- other fees and income sources (around 10 per cent of total operational income).

Capital transfers for investments are not listed but have been as high as current transfers in the past years as current transfers in absolute values.

A major share of municipal budgets comes from intragovernmental transfers, a complex system of re-distribution of revenues across all levels of government regulated in the Fiscal Equalization Act (*Finanzausgleichsgesetz, FAG*), which is negotiated every three to eight years between the three levels of administration.⁴⁸ This act defines the amount of shared revenues municipalities are granted. One of the main criteria of distribution is the tiered population scheme which reflects changes in population in a nonlinear way. Based on this scheme, urban municipalities with larger populations receive a larger share of the revenues. Shared revenues are mainly comprised of shares out of taxes like the value added tax (VAT), income tax and

⁴⁸ See Johann Bröthaler, Anita Haindl and Karoline Mitterer, 'Funktionsweisen und finanzielle Entwicklungen im Finanzausgleichssystem' in Helfried Bauer and others (eds), *Finanzausgleich 2017: Ein Handbuch* (NWV 2017).

corporate tax. In total around 15 per cent of shared revenues are allocated to municipalities in the context of fiscal equalization.⁴⁹ Shared taxes amounted to EUR 6.7 billion in 2018 for the local governments (without the Capital City of Vienna).⁵⁰

In addition to shared revenues, local taxes are an important factor of municipal income. The most important local tax for municipalities' budgets is the 'municipality tax'. Companies based in Austria have to pay municipality tax amounting to 3 per cent of the total sum of salaries paid within one month. Therefore, municipalities with higher employment have higher municipality tax income. In general, this applies stronger to urban local governments (ULGs) and municipalities with a strong tourism industry. Property tax is levied on individuals owning property, the amount is set by the municipalities considering a legal tax cap. As there has not been a reform since 1973, the property tax is currently under revision and likely to be reformed in the next years.⁵¹ Municipality tax amounted to about EUR 2.5 billion in 2018 whereas property tax amounted to about EUR 600 million (all municipalities except Vienna).⁵²

Besides shared revenues there is a further intragovernmental transfer system between municipalities and the federal and *Länder* level. Each *Land* determines a levy that all municipalities must transfer, e.g. in order to finance the hospitals run by the *Länder*. In return, the *Länder* and also the national government distribute transfers to support municipal investments. These transfers can be divided into current transfers and capital transfers. Current transfers are meant to finance the maintaining of public services. Capital transfers however are purposed to allow for investments in infrastructure for example. Current transfers amounted to EUR 1.6 billion in 2018 with current transfers from the federal level amounting to 20 per cent and from the *Länder* level to 60 per cent. Municipalities that are not able to break even their budgets (e.g. because of losses in municipality tax revenue or structural issues) are granted additional transfers from the *Länder* to cover the deficit. However, all further investments are subject to approval by the *Länder* level, who monitors the municipality until a sustainable and balanced budget is reached. Through this transfer system, rural local governments (RLGs) benefit stronger as levies are higher for municipalities with more income.

Fees are mainly generated through the provision of public services and utilities such as water, sewerage and waste. There are, however, local authority associations that carry out these services and have their own budget. In this case municipalities make proportionate payments to cover the costs of the associations.

⁴⁹ *ibid.*

⁵⁰ See Österreichischer Städtebund (ed), 'Stadtdialog. Schriftenreihe des Österreichischen Städtebundes, Gemeindefinanzen 2020 – Entwicklungen 2009 – 2023' (forthcoming).

⁵¹ See Peter Mühlberger and Siegfried Ott, *Die Kommunen im Finanz- und Steuerrecht* (1st edn, DBV 2016); René Geißler and Falk Ebinger, 'Austria' in René Geißler, Gerhard Hammerschmid and Christian Raffer (eds), *Local Public Finance in Europe. Country Reports* (Bertelsmann Stiftung 2019).

⁵² See Österreichischer Städtebund, 'Stadtdialog', above.

To conclude, important expenditure-incurring tasks such as health care and social protection happen at subnational level, but a minor share is financed through municipal revenues. As a result, municipalities are financially dependent mainly on the shared tax transfers (*Ertragsanteile*) by higher levels of government due to the significant mismatch between revenue raising power and expenditure responsibilities.⁵³ While the shared tax transfers and local tax incomes are higher in ULGs, after the mandatory transfer (levies, current and capital transfers) the income of RLGs becomes more level with that of urban ones.

Public Spending and Debt

Municipalities cover a wide arrange of tasks from the construction and maintenance of streets to kindergartens, primary schools, residential care homes for elderly people and services like water supply, sewerage and waste disposal.⁵⁴ Highest expenditures are carried out in the fields of services (e.g. water, sewerage, waste), welfare and education.⁵⁵ Expenditure has to follow the approved budget. If deviations from the budget occur (e.g. because of unforeseen projects) municipalities have to prepare a revised budget and gain the approval of the local council.

In general, municipalities are only allowed to take on long-term debt for capital spending. Current expenditures cannot be covered with long-term debt. There are rules for short-term loans which have to be paid back within the fiscal year. Furthermore, *Länder* law prohibits the use of risky financial instruments. Over the last ten years municipal debt slightly rose from EUR 11.5 billion in 2009 to 11.6 billion in 2018.⁵⁶

Recent Developments

Until 2019 Austrian municipalities followed the rules of a cameralistic system. The budgeting and accounting were done according to a cash-flow oriented system. From 2020 on an accrual system is now implemented. The income statement shows the resource flows within the municipality. The cash flow statement shows the cash inflows and outflows. The balance sheet includes balances of assets, accounts receivable, accounts payable, loans etc. With this shift to a more resource-oriented concept a holistic assessment of municipal accounting is possible.⁵⁷

⁵³ European Commission, 'Country Report Austria 2019' COM (2019) 150 final.

⁵⁴ See Geißler and Ebinger, 'Austria', above.

⁵⁵ See Österreichischer Städtebund, 'Stadtdialog', above.

⁵⁶ *ibid.*

⁵⁷ See Robert Blöschl, Clemens Hödl and Alexander Maimer, 'Mit der VRV 2015 zu mehr Generationengerechtigkeit' in Peter Biwald and others (eds), *Nachhaltig wirken. Impulse für den öffentlichen Sektor* (NWV 2019).

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